

Horizon 2020 Program (2014-2020)

Big data PPP

Research addressing main technology challenges of the data economy.

Industrial-Driven Big Data as a Self-Service Solution

Deliverable 7.1: Project Website

Abstract: This deliverable presents the work performed in WP7/Task7.2 “Communication strategy triggering awareness and new business opportunities” with respect to design and development of the I-BiDaaS website to public use. Since the aim of WP7 is supervising the integrity and consistency of all dissemination efforts for creating awareness on the I-BiDaaS developments, the main objective of this deliverable is to develop the underlying infrastructure in order to effectively establish the I-BiDaaS online presence for reaching out to the widest possible audiences and provide a consistent source of information for all kind of dissemination efforts.

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Caixabank S.A.	Principal Contractor	Spain
University of Manchester	Principal Contractor	United Kingdom
Ecole Nationale des Ponts et Chaussees	Principal Contractor	France
ATOS Spain S.A.	Principal Contractor	Spain
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1 Executive summary

This document reports on the work executed in WP7/Task7.2 “Communication strategy triggering awareness and new business opportunities” in terms of design and development of the I-BiDaaS website. Within the framework of the general Dissemination Strategy of I-BiDaaS project, the current website is defined as an effective web-based working space and collaboration portal where information and knowledge can be shared between various stakeholders and any other interested end users. In brief, the document gives an overview of the project website, its structure and main features.

1.1 Introduction

I-BiDaaS website has been designed and developed by ITML. The developing activities have been started in M1 while at the beginning of M2 it was already ready for full operation. The website contains information about the project’s objectives, consortium, main domains, and platform. The website’s updating activities have been proceeding in a regular basis, by circulating information about all the events and promotional materials as I-BiDaaS progresses. The latter is taking place in close collaboration with dissemination manager, WP leaders, and Scientific/Technical coordinator. In the following sections the website design, technical information, overall structure and characteristic screenshots are illustrated in more details.

2 I-BiDaaS website

2.1 Overview

The project website follows a person-centric approach meaning that it is very user-focused. The website includes:

- Concept and main characteristics introduction
- Consortium introduction
- Public availability to all the project results (including all publications, dissemination materials, presentations, deliverables)
- Posting the project news and events in regular basis

2.2 Technical details

Domain: <http://www.ibidaas.eu/>

Servers/hosting: Linux based Apache 2.4.6

Content Management System (CMS) type: Drupal Version 8.4.4

PHP Version 7.1.14

MySQL Version 5.5.56

2.3 Website structure

The website has a simple structure as it is illustrated in Figure 1, opening up to a portal which focuses on acting as a social single-entry point where users can network and push dissemination information, at the same time. Information will be offered by many means and the necessary features incorporated, will support the information flow from one user to another, thus creating a network of social activity. The importance of social networking relates to the outcome of increasing traffic to the website, as well as increasing awareness of the site purpose, scientific context and purpose of the project, as well as pilot applications and outcomes.

Figure 1: I-BiDaaS website structure.

2.4 Graphic design

The website utilizes the approved project logo and high-resolution images (received from partners).

Figure 2: I-BiDaaS logo.

The look and design of the website (Figure 3) has been carefully discussed with corporate internal professionals, who have ended up with the proposed schemes, which are obviously linked with the graphic identity of the project (logo). Moreover, the website is fully responsive and follows all relevant W3C guidelines regarding accessibility, ensuring that it can be accessed by as many people as possible regardless of their capabilities and by as many devices as possible regardless of their screen resolution or other features.

Figure 3: I-BiDaaS main page.

2.5 I-BiDaaS website content

2.5.1 Home

The Home section includes general project information. It contains four sub-sections namely project objectives, platform, domains, and project work plan (Figure 3). It also includes a partners moving sidebar and a footer as shown in Figure 4 and Figure 5 respectively.

Figure 4: Moving sidebar of I-BiDaaS consortium.

Figure 5: Disclaimer on Webpage Footer.

The Disclaimer page lists the key facts of the project, including the website main menus, links to the social networks, details about the received funding as well as link and the logo of BIG DATA value partnership.

In Figure 6 and Figure 7 the screenshots of project platform and work plan are illustrated.

The I-BiDaaS platform is illustrated below:

Figure 6: I-BiDaaS platform page.

Based on the overall strategy for the I-BiDaaS work plan, the work to be performed in the project will be realised in a set of work packages illustrated below.

Work Packages

1. Setting the scene: Baseline framework
2. Data curation ingestion and pre-processing
3. Batch processing innovative technologies for rapidly increasing historical data
4. Distributed analytics over extremely large numbers of high volume streams
5. Distributed large scale framework and integration
6. Real-life industrial and operational experiments
7. Exploitation, sustainability and business continuity
8. Project management

Figure 7: I-BiDaaS work plan page.

2.5.2 Consortium

The consortium section presents the overall partners map, as shown in Figure 8, as well as the partners' logos, short description and links to their main page.

The consortium includes partners from eight (8) European countries: France, Germany, Greece, Spain, Serbia, Italy, the United Kingdom, and Israel.

The map shows the following partner locations and logos: Manchester (UK), AEGIS (UK), software AG (Germany), Ecole des Ponts (France), Atos (Spain), Telefonica (Spain), CaixaBank (Spain), CENTRO RICERCHI FIAT (Italy), FORTH (Greece), IBM (Israel), and IBM (USA).

FOUNDATION FOR RESEARCH AND TECHNOLOGY HELLAS (FORTH)
The Foundation for Research and Technology - Hellas established in 1983, is the largest Greek State R&D Centre. FORTH hosts six major Research Institutes. The Institute of Computer Science (ICS) has established an internationally acknowledged excellence in conducting basic and applied research, developing applications and products, and providing services.

BARCELONA SUPERCOMPUTING CENTER (BSC)
The Barcelona Supercomputing Center was established in 2005 and is the Spanish national supercomputing facility and a hosting member of the PRACE distributed supercomputing infrastructure. The Center houses MareNostrum, one of the most powerful supercomputers in Europe. The mission of BSC is to research, develop and manage information technologies in order to facilitate scientific progress.

IBM ISRAEL - SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY LTD (IBM)
IBM Israel Science and Technology, better known as IBM Research - Haifa, was first established in 1972. Since then, the lab has conducted decades of research vital to IBM's success. The lab is one of 9 research laboratories located outside of the United States, and has close working relationships with IBM Israel and its twin research laboratory in Zurich.

CENTRO RICERCHI FIAT (CRF)
Centro Ricerche Fiat is one of the main private research centres in Italy. It was founded in 1978, with the mission to develop and transfer innovative products, processes and methodologies in order to improve the competitiveness of the products of FCA (FIAT Chrysler Automobiles).

SOFTWARE AG (SAG)
Software AG offers the first end-to-end Digital Business Platform, based on open standards, with integration, process management, in-memory data, adaptive application development, real-time analytics and enterprise architecture management as core building blocks. The modular platform allows users to develop the next generation of application systems to build their digital future, today.

Figure 8: I-BiDaaS consortium page.

2.5.3 Downloads

The section downloads containing four additional sub-menus (deliverables, presentations, publications and dissemination materials) will collect all the project results, publications, presentation and all the relevant dissemination materials in line with project outcome results.

Figure 9: I-BiDaaS downloads page.

2.5.4 News

This section will provide regular updates about I-BiDaaS project containing all the news and events in which project partners attend and present the project.

Figure 10: I-BiDaaS news page.

2.5.5 Contact

This section allows the visitors to submit their messages and feedback directly to I-BiDaaS administrative sector. Depending on the context, the messages will be directed to the corresponding technical or communication representatives of I-BiDaaS.

A contact form with the following fields and buttons:

- Your name ***: A text input field.
- Your email address ***: A text input field.
- Subject ***: A text input field.
- Message ***: A large text area for the message content.
- SEND MESSAGE**: A button to submit the form.
- PREVIEW**: A button to preview the message.

Figure 11: Contact page.

2.5.6 Social Media

The website will include links to social media (Twitter, LinkedIn).

Figure 12: Social media icons.

2.6 Upcoming updates

Currently the website is in its initial version. As the project progresses, the website will be enriched with more information. According to the proposed timeplan, the I-BiDaaS website will be upgraded by M8, in terms of functionality and graphical content.